

Sample 28a

Greyscale Image

141 μm

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0000
	{Si}	59.2
	{Fe}	15.4
	{Al, Si}	7.5
	{Si, Ca LoP}	2.6
	{Al, Si, Ca}	2.4
	{Si, Fe}	2.0
	{Ca}	1.5
	{Al, Si, K}	1.5
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	1.2
	{Al}	0.8
	{Si, Ca HIP}	0.8
	{Na, Al, Si}	0.6
	{Si, K}	0.5
	{Ca, Fe}	0.5
	{Mg, Si}	0.4
	{Ti}	0.4
	{Mg, Ca}	0.4
	{P, Ca}	0.3
	{Al, Ca}	0.3
	{S, Ca}	0.3
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.3
	{Na, Si}	0.2
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.1
	{Mg, Fe}	0.1
	{Si, Fe}	0.1
	{Al, Si, Fe}	0.1
	{Cl}	0.1
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.1
	{P}	0.1
	{S}	0.1
	{Cr, Fe}	0.1
	{Mg, Si, Fe}	0.1
	{Al, Fe}	0.0
	{Si, Cl}	0.0

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	1.2
Pellet	1.8
Ore preparation undifferentiated	5.6
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.9
BOF converter slag	0.4
BOF converter slag slopping	0.1
Slag BOF converter or desulph	3.1
Desulph slag	0.4
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.3
Olivine flux	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.5
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.5
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.1
Coal and cokes or soil	21.8
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	2.1
Carbon rich - other	5.7
Cement or BOF converter	0.0
Cement	0.3
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.2
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	45.1
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	8.9
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.3
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.4
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.3

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	8.6
Site - ore / hot metal	0.9
Site - slag	4.0
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.3
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	0.5
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.5
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.1
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	21.8
Site - carbon-rich other	2.1
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	5.7
Urban, rarely site - slag	0.0
Urban	0.5
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	45.1
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	8.9
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.3
Unknown	0.4
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.3

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 28b

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0114
	{Si}	50.0
	{Fe}	20.6
	{Al, Si}	8.4
	{Ca, Fe}	2.4
	{Si, Fe}	2.3
	{Si, Ca LoP}	1.8
	{Ca}	1.8
	{Al, Si, Ca}	1.6
	{Na, Al, Si}	1.5
	{Al, Si, K}	1.2
	{Al}	0.9
	{Si, Ca HIP}	0.8
	{Mg, Si}	0.8
	{Ti}	0.6
	{Cl}	0.6
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.5
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.4
	{Mg, Ca}	0.4
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.3
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.3
	{Na, Si}	0.3
	{Al, Ca}	0.3
	{Si, K}	0.2
	{Zn-LA1}	0.2
	{Mg, Fe}	0.2
	{Si, Cl}	0.2
	{Al, Si, P}	0.2
	{Si, Fe}	0.2
	{Al, Si, Fe}	0.1
	{S, Ca}	0.1
	{Al, Fe}	0.1
	{S}	0.1
	{Mg, Si, Fe}	0.1
	{Mg}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	3.8
Pellet	3.4
Ore preparation undifferentiated	7.4
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.8
BOF converter slag	0.0
BOF converter slag slopping	0.2
Slag BOF converter or desulph	1.4
Desulph slag	0.4
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.4
Olivine flux	0.4
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.2
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.1
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.4
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.3
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	24.4
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	1.7
Carbon rich - other	6.1
Cement or BOF converter	0.6
Cement	0.4
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	0.1
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	38.4
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	9.0
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.1

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	14.6
Site - ore / hot metal	0.8
Site - slag	2.0
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.8
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	0.2
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.5
Site - scrap	0.3
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	24.4
Site - carbon-rich other	1.7
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	6.1
Urban, rarely site - slag	0.6
Urban	0.5
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	38.4
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	9.0
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.1

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 28c

Greyscale Image

141 μm

PARC Phases

	area %
{Pb-rich}	0.0000
{Si}	60.8
{Fe}	15.2
{Al, Si}	9.6
{Al, Si, K}	2.0
{Si, Fe}	1.7
{Na, Al, Si}	1.7
{Ca, Fe}	1.1
{Mg, Si}	0.8
{Si, Ca LoP}	0.8
{Al, Si, Ca}	0.8
{Ca}	0.7
{Si, Ca HIP}	0.6
{Al}	0.5
{Na, Si}	0.4
{Si, K}	0.4
{Ti}	0.3
{Mg, Al, Si}	0.3
{Cl}	0.3
{Al, Ca}	0.2
{S, Ca}	0.2
{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.1
{Mg, Fe}	0.1
{Si, Fe}	0.1
{Si, Cl}	0.1
{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.1
{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.1
{Al, Si, Fe}	0.1
{Mg, Ca}	0.1
{Mg, Al}	0.1
{S}	0.1
{Ti, Fe}	0.0
{Mg, Si, Fe}	0.0
{Al, Fe}	0.0
{Si, S, Ca}	0.0

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	1.8
Pellet	0.5
Ore preparation undifferentiated	3.0
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	1.2
BOF converter slag	0.0
BOF converter slag slopping	0.2
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.3
Desulph slag	0.0
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.0
Olivine flux	0.2
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.0
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.1
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	30.8
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	2.4
Carbon rich - other	6.9
Cement or BOF converter	0.0
Cement	0.2
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	0.2
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.3
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	44.3
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	7.3
Misc silicates including natural	0.1
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.0

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	5.3
Site - ore / hot metal	1.2
Site - slag	0.5
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.2
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	0.0
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.1
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	30.8
Site - carbon-rich other	2.4
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	6.9
Urban, rarely site - slag	0.0
Urban	0.7
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	44.3
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	7.3
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.1
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/o partial chloride cover)	0.0

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels